

The CASPER project approach towards user-centric mobile networks

Eirini Liotou¹, Dimitris Tsolkas¹, Stefano Tennina², Luigi Pomante³, and Giorgos Kalpatsoglou⁴

¹Department of Informatics & Telecommunications, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Greece

²WEST Aquila S.r.l., L'Aquila, Italy

³Università degli Studi dell'Aquila, L'Aquila, Italy

⁴ADAPTERA, Athens, Greece

Abstract—This paper presents an overview of the project CASPER¹, a Marie Curie Research and Innovation Staff Exchange (RISE) project running from 2016 until 2020. The main objective of CASPER is to combine academic and industrial forces towards leveraging the expected benefits of Quality of Experience (QoE) exploitation in future digital networks. In particular, CASPER exploits the most recent advances in communication networks, such as the Software Defined Networking (SDN) and the Network Functions Virtualisation (NFV) in order to design and implement a middleware architecture for QoE-driven service provisioning. CASPER, therefore, addresses the challenges that mobile network operators and service providers face in the current fully digitalized era of communications, concerning the need to provide customer-oriented, reliable, efficient, flexible and dynamic service management.

Keywords—Quality of Experience, NFV, SDN, orchestration.

I. INTRODUCTION

CASPER (“A user-Centric middleware Architecture for advanced Service Provisioning in futurE netwoRks”) is a Research and Innovation Staff Exchange (RISE) project under Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (2016-2020). CASPER aims at bringing together experts from industry and academia, from cross-sectorial research areas having complementary background, with the goal of analysing and exploiting Quality of Experience (QoE) towards developing efficient schemes for managing multimedia digital services. In particular, special attention is devoted to the development of innovative QoE estimation mechanisms and QoE monitoring protocols for optimizing service delivery and providing key input to Customer Experience Management (CEM) policies. CASPER has created a fully-integrated and multi-disciplinary program on the development of QoE network optimisation modules towards the creation of a programmable, re-configurable and adaptable architecture.

QoE is defined by the International Telecommunication Union - Telecommunication Standardization Sector (ITU-T) Rec. P.10 (Amendment 2, 2008), as “the overall acceptability of an application or service, as perceived subjectively by the end-user”. This concept has emerged due to the inefficiency of the traditional Quality of Service (QoS) term to fully imprint the actual experience of the end-users, as well as its inability to fully capture application-specific and user-specific characteristics. The purpose of the QoE concept is, therefore, to provide means to track the degree of user satisfaction of a network’s performance in a qualitative or quantitative manner and to try to improve it in order to meet or exceed the users’ expectations. In order to guarantee QoE in a network, three procedures need to be implemented [1]:

a) **QoE modelling**: It refers to an estimation method that attempts to quantify the level of user experience and imprint it into a Mean Opinion Score (MOS) or a collection of values for Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). There are various different approaches for estimating QoE. Their primary classification is into objective and subjective models. Subjective models are based on real life experiments with human participants who evaluate their experience of an application or service. Objective models, on the other hand, try to automatically measure or predict the quality perceived by the end-users, without their intervention and are, therefore, required for real-time service evaluation.

b) **QoE monitoring**: It refers to the key functionality of gathering network, application and user-related factors required for a reliable estimation of the end-user’s satisfaction level. These factors refer to service evaluation feedback from the end-user and from parameters available in diverse network entities (user device, access network, service provider) and in all protocol layers. For the gathering of these factors, active (intrusive) and passive (non-intrusive) monitoring schemes can be used, while only a specific set of factors is monitored depending on the specifications of the used estimation model.

c) **QoE management**: It refers to methods, protocols and techniques that aim to enhance the customer experience, while in parallel making efficient use of network resources (e.g. [2]). The available service management procedures for QoE management include but are not limited to routing, scheduling, admission control, rate adaptation, and network selection. Such procedures, especially for multimedia services, are currently bounded by QoS limitations that rely on network constraints (e.g., available spectrum). The QoE factor is, therefore, the key for moving beyond QoS thresholds and acquiring at the same time the levels of end-users’ satisfaction for a provided service.

CASPER proposes a paradigm in order to integrate the three aforementioned procedures and to guarantee the user experience in modern networks. It consists of three interlinked and optimised modules applied both in user and network plane, dealing with the QoE monitoring, estimation, and management functionalities. The QoE provisioning logic exploits the flexibility and re-configurability provided by the Network Functions Virtualisation (NFV) and Software-Defined Networking (SDN) technology in a bidirectional manner to acquire QoE influence factors from anchor points in the network and to apply QoE-driven service management policies. A twofold target has been set for the three interlinked functionalities: i) to personalise service delivery through acquiring and combining knowledge available in distributed places, such as various network elements in the access/core/backhaul network, as well as in databases, human subjects and surrounding environments, and ii) to

¹ <http://gain.di.uoa.gr/casper/>

Fig. 1: A mapping of the key Functional Modules for QoE provisioning on the mobile network infrastructure

motivate providers to use enhanced QoE-driven service management policies as well as advanced CEM techniques. A mapping of the key functional modules for QoE provisioning on the mobile network infrastructure, as proposed by CASPER, is depicted in Fig. 1.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the project objectives, while Section III describes its concept and targeted scenarios. Then, Section IV provides the CASPER implementation methodology. Section V presents the main achievements of the project, namely: a) a user-centric orchestration architecture, b) a QoE modelling tool, c) a QoE monitoring methodology for managing multimedia flows, as well as d) a system level simulator and e) a testbed for experimentation of user-centric management scenarios. Finally, Section VI briefly describes the project's consortium, while Section VII concludes the paper.

II. PROJECT MISSION AND OBJECTIVES

CASPER has three main research objectives:

1. To study, design and optimise QoE estimation mechanisms for multimedia services. This main scientific objective includes mechanisms for subjective and objective evaluation of a provided service. The target is to enhance and optimise QoE estimation models, to thoroughly study and evaluate key indicators that affect the QoE, and to design efficient and dynamic schemes for QoS to QoE translation.
2. To study, design, and optimise QoE monitoring protocols. This objective includes the thorough study of next generation network architecture and protocol stack towards defining the anchor points from where key QoE indicators can be acquired and the communication protocols for gathering those at network and user plane. The achievement of this objective is expected to provide an essential module to operators for exploiting the knowledge of their customers' experience.
3. To analyse, design and optimise advanced QoE-driven service management policies. An innovative and stochastic representation of the future networks, including the recent advances in SDN and NFV for orchestrating service provisioning is used for designing cross-layer QoE-driven service management policies. Additionally, by capitalizing on the QoE-awareness at operators/service providers and end-devices, application layer enhancements are provided at user plane for more personalised service delivery.

In addition, CASPER's main technological objectives are:

1. To develop a System Level Simulator (SLS), where the QoE estimation and monitoring schemes, and the QoE-driven service management policies will be evaluated under realistic scenarios.
2. To develop a hardware proof-of-concept testbed, where the most promising schemes identified via the SLS will be integrated and tested in a real-working environment.
3. To integrate QoE exploitation functions into real devices, where a meaningful subset of the middleware architecture will be implemented in commercial devices and network entities for real-life experimentation.

III. CONCEPT AND APPROACH

The main objective of CASPER is the design and implementation of a middleware architecture for QoE-driven service provisioning. The first goal towards this objective is the identification of the distinct stakeholders involved in this architecture who can, therefore, benefit from it. Three main stakeholders can be distinguished in the investigated service provisioning paradigm, namely the Over-The-Top Service Providers (OTT), the Mobile Network Operators (MNO) or Internet Service Providers (ISP) and, finally the end-users (Fig. 2). The end-users are the final consumers of a service, which is provided either by the MNO directly or by an OTT service provider through the MNO's infrastructure. Other parties such as vendors or cloud infrastructure providers are also considered as available wherever needed in CASPER. CASPER defines and studies three main scenarios which involve the aforementioned stakeholders, while different service types (e.g. VoIP and video) are considered per scenario.

Fig. 2: The main stakeholders in CASPER

The first CASPER scenario refers to real-time communication between two parties that is end-to-end supported by the infrastructure of the MNO. The involved parties (end-users) have connectivity to the same or different operators (intra-operator and inter-operator cases, respectively) and they may be located in the same or different cells (Fig. 3 – Scenario A). Table I summarises the major principles of scenario A.

Fig. 3: Abstract representation of CASPER scenarios (only inter-operator cases are presented)

TABLE I. SCENARIO A

Scenario A	
Modules involved	SDN modules, QoE manager
Service type	Real time (VoIP or video)
Involved users	Two communicating peers
Technical challenge	Apply network-side optimisations to guarantee high level of QoE at both peers
Approach	Advanced routing of the data flows
Interface(s) / Components used to apply the policy	OpenDaylight API
Parameters to be monitored - service level	Packet loss ratio, Latency, Jitter, Codec, and Coding rate
Parameters to be monitored - network level	SDN data and control plane parameters (e.g., Packet Latency, Transmit/Receive Throughput Rate, Connected OpenFlow Switches)
QoE manager feeding approach	ELK module (querying the elasticsearch)

Scenario B concerns cases of video content delivery, namely video streaming from an OTT service provider. The common paradigm nowadays is that OTT parties provide access to video streaming services, which the users can access only through their MNO or ISP connection. (Note that MNOs or ISPs may also provide video streaming services by themselves to their subscribers). The second scenario of CASPER is depicted in Fig. 3 as well. The main service that may be applied to this scenario is video streaming (Non-adaptive or HTTP adaptive video streaming), i.e., a non-real-time service. Caching video content is an important feature of this scenario. Table II summarises the major principles of Scenario B.

TABLE II. SCENARIO B

Scenario B	
Modules involved	SDN modules, NFV modules, QoE manager
Service type	Video Streaming
Involved users	A user that consumes video on demand

Technical challenge	a) Apply end-to-end service optimizations b) Apply content delivery optimizations
Approach	a) Proper transcoding of video content b) Content instantiation using CDN and caching techniques
Interface(s) / Components used to apply the policy	OpenStack and OpenDaylight
Parameters to be monitored - service level	Data rate, Video bit rate, Media bit rate, Number of stalling events, Duration of stalling events, Initial delay, Video start failure, Time on highest layer, Frequency of quality switches, Amplitude of switches
Parameters to be monitored - network level	SDN data and control plane parameters (e.g., Packet Latency, Transmit/Receive Throughput Rate, Connected OpenFlow Switches)
QoE manager feeding approach	ELK module (querying the elasticsearch) User application layer

The third scenario is the most challenging one since it includes an OTT provider, one or more MNO/ISP providers and multiple users. Applications that fall into this category are online meetings, video conferencing and in general shared collaborative platforms. The traffic in this case is accumulated at a server in the possession of the OTT party, passing however through the network infrastructure of one or more MNO/ISPs (intra-operator and inter-operator case, respectively). This scenario is summarised in Table III. More information about the CASPER scenarios are available at [2].

TABLE III. SCENARIO C

Scenario C	
Modules involved	SDN modules, NFV modules, Big Data analytics, QoE manager
Service type	Online meeting (e.g., WebEx with independent voice and video streams), or many diverse service types of multiple competing users
Involved users	Multiple users at different locations
Technical challenge	Global flow optimizations
Approach	Apply proper but differentiated routing of voice and video streams (e.g., WebEx) Functions/Content instantiation based on KPI requirements (e.g., users streaming simultaneously a very popular video)
Interface(s) / Components used to apply the policy	Custom API, OpenStack, and OpenDaylight
Parameters to be monitored - service level	All parameters of scenarios A and B
Parameters to be monitored - network level	SDN data and control plane parameters (e.g., Packet Latency, Transmit/Receive Throughput Rate, Connected OpenFlow Switches, Memory utilization)
QoE manager feeding approach	ELK module (querying the elasticsearch)

IV. IMPLEMENTATION AND WORK PACKAGES

CASPER methodology encompasses four main phases. These phases, together with their encompassed Work Packages (WP) are depicted at Fig. 4 and are further described below. The project is currently within its Phase 3. **Phase-1: Middleware architecture and QoE analysis and exploitation schemes.** During this phase, academic and industrial beneficiaries have worked in synergy to design the middleware architecture for QoE service delivery. In particular, all beneficiaries were responsible to define the requirements of the middleware architecture, the key parameters for QoE estimation/monitoring and the reconfigurable parameters used in the QoE-aware service

management. Attention was given on defining potential hardware limitations and interoperability/energy/privacy issues, while innovative QoE estimation mechanisms, QoE monitoring protocols, and service management algorithms were developed. The methodology for this phase consisted of two steps: i) define the middleware architecture and a set of quality indicators used for QoE estimation/monitoring; and ii) design QoE estimation mechanisms and monitoring protocols, and QoE-driven service management policies.

Phase-2: Analysis and optimisation of the QoE provision schemes using simulations. This phase included the development of a System Level Simulator (SLS) based on the QoE architecture designed in Phase-1. Using this simulator, the algorithms and protocols proposed in Phase-1 have been evaluated and optimised. The methodology adopted in this phase consisted of three main steps: i) the translation of the algorithms and protocols developed in Phase-1 in fundamental modules written in the programming language of the SLS; ii) the integration of the modules into the SLS in order to realise the proposed middleware architecture; and iii) the performance assessment in the project scenarios and the comparison with benchmark solutions by taking into account the project's service performance evaluation metrics.

Phase-3: Implementation, proof-of-concept study, and experimental assessment. During the third phase, the modules defined in Phase-2 are being applied in a testbed and their performance is going to be evaluated through a measurement campaign in a realistic working environment. This phase is considered critical before the implementation in real devices, in order to gain: i) a very clear understanding of the requirements for applying the proposed solutions to real environments, ii) an understanding of the capabilities and limitations of the new solutions, iii) the ability to assess design decisions early in the process, and iv) the ability to a-priori visualise the look-and-feel of the solutions. In this way, reduction in the overall risk of the project implementation will be achieved. The main goal is to clarify the maturity of the new system including: i) what can be supported or not by the implemented middleware architecture, ii) if the technology is strong enough to be deployed and achieve foreseen performances, iii) if these solutions can be used on existing wireless and mobile networks. The methodology for this phase consists of the following steps: i) the testbed implementation and upgrade with the innovative algorithms and protocols; ii) the definition of test scenarios, metrics and targeted values; iii) the execution of scenarios and extraction of measurements; and iv) the evaluation of results and conclusions.

Phase-4: Product integration in commercial devices and realistic experiments. In the fourth and last phase, a meaningful subset of the middleware architecture with the QoE estimation and service management modules will be integrated into real devices that will be made available by the industrial beneficiaries. Compared with Phase-3, real-life measurement scenarios will be defined, covering scalability, reliability, real-time applicability and performance issues under a wide range of conditions. Subjective on-site measurements or crowd-sourcing techniques may be considered for the evaluation of the quality of the integrated solution. The methodology for this phase will consist of the following steps: i) integration of a

meaningful subset of the middleware architecture into real devices; ii) execution of real-life scenarios and experiments; iii) assessment of the developed system.

Fig. 4: Workpackages and implementation phases

The project is organised into 7 work packages (WPs), as shown in Fig. 4. WP1 and WP7 are concerned with management and dissemination respectively, running for the whole duration of the project. The rest WPs, from WP2 to WP6, are the technical WPs of the project. More specifically, WP2 is concerned with the definition of the overall middleware architecture and the requirements for exploiting QoE in future networks; WP3 focuses on the analysis of key quality indicators, and the design of QoE estimation mechanisms and QoE monitoring protocols; WP4 performs the design and optimisation of the QoE-driven service management policies; WP5 deals with the implementation and validation of algorithms/protocols in the system level simulator and the testbed; and finally WP6 handles the final integration in commercial devices and proof-of-concept in a real-working environment. In detail:

WP2 (Middleware architecture definition and requirements description) objectives: *To provide an end-to-end description of the middleware architecture and ensure its smooth and realistic applicability in commercial products by taking into consideration real-life systems' requirements, such as performance, complexity, hardware, and energy constraints.* The tasks of WP2 include the description of various communication scenarios and the definition of target performance metrics and key parameters. Moreover, WP2 includes the design of the complete middleware architecture that thoroughly describes the new modules, methods and functionalities required to be implemented inside real devices and providers' infrastructure.

WP3 (QoE estimation mechanisms and QoE monitoring protocols) objectives: *To set the ground for the implementation of the enhanced QoE support framework, by providing the theoretical findings regarding QoE estimation and monitoring options.* The tasks in this WP include the identification of the QoE influence factors and the investigation of possible options for QoE modelling. Moreover, research focuses on the monitoring options in smart devices using for instance software agents or present capabilities of the devices as well as deal with the available monitoring options at the service provider's side (routing devices or provider's management nodes). Finally, this WP defines and simulates a protocol for the dissemination of

information from the various monitoring and estimation locations to the service provider’s service management nodes.

WP4 (Design and optimisation of QoE-driven service management policies) objectives: *To define the basic QoE management framework and to design optimisation and control algorithms for enhanced service provisioning.* This WP designs a management framework that will be used by the service providers and operators in order to exploit the acquired QoE-related information for their own as well as for their customers’ benefit. The framework is designed on top of NFV/SDN technologies under the control of a centric QoE orchestrator. Moreover, WP4 defines the CEM scenarios to be applied to the QoE management support, and investigates advanced policies based on acquired QoE measurements.

WP5 (Development and validation of proposed modules) objectives: *To integrate simulation modules of WP3 and WP4 and conduct joint simulations, followed by the development of building blocks for the respective algorithms and protocols.* In WP5, the separate simulation modules, constructed during WP3 and WP4 and offering measurements on the performance of individual solutions, are integrated into one overall simulation model. Next, WP5 translates these algorithms and protocols into modules /building blocks which will be then directly integrated into the nodes of the testbed in order to conduct detailed experimental activities for a preliminary proof-of-concept of the proposed middleware architecture.

WP6 (System integration and proof-of-concept) objectives: *To integrate the proposed architecture into real devices and to test the performance in real working environments. This will provide a clear assessment of advantages/disadvantages of the proposed solutions.* In this WP, a meaningful set of the modules/building blocks identified, developed, and tested in WP5 will be integrated into real devices. Moreover, WP6 will perform a comprehensive experimental assessment of the developed devices improved with the new middleware and evaluate the performance improvement in realistic environments where the devices are expected to operate.

V. MAIN ACHIEVEMENTS

A. CASPER orchestration architecture

CASPER orchestration logic is integrated into the ETSI NFV-MANO architecture (Management and Orchestration Architecture) [4] as shown at Fig. 5. The proposed QoE orchestrator acts as the NFV Orchestrator (NFVO) and is logically divided into three components which include the basic functionalities of QoE modelling, monitoring and service management. The QoE controller, in addition, as its name implies, controls the collection of monitored information from the various network entities into the QoE orchestrator.

The flow of QoE service management in CASPER is as follows:

1. The QoE monitor requests KPIs from the QoE controller
2. Each ELK collects appropriate information from the VNF that it is in charge of
3. The QoE controller creates respective queries to these ELKs

4. These requests are handled by the appropriate ELK
5. Monitored parameters are reported back to the QoE controller
6. The QoE monitor translates collected information to QoE “language” (i.e. MOS or KPI values vs. appropriate thresholds)
7. Network and/or application management mechanisms are triggered by the QoE manager, using for instance OpenStack (which acts as the Virtualized Infrastructure Manager) or OpenDaylight (which acts as the SDN controller and Virtual Networking Manager).

Fig. 5: QoE orchestration in CASPER [5]

B. CASPER QoE modelling tool

To facilitate the analysis on QoE estimation, in the context of CASPER we developed a tool that uses, as a key interface with the end-users, a mobile application. A storyline for the usage of this tool is as follows:

- The mobile application is used to monitor and store to a database, video delivery characteristics (such as initial delay, stalling events etc.) and network characteristics (such as the connection type).
- The user / video consumer is requested by the application to evaluate the presented video by giving a MOS score. The value provided by the user is also stored to the database.
- The collected data (user’s feedback and monitored values) are then analyzed using machine learning techniques to set a mathematic formula that translates monitored parameters to a QoE score.

Fig. 6: Storyboard of the CASPER application

The procedure to be used for the data collection is based on specifications for subjective QoE tests and current work on crowdsourcing practices. A storyboard of the application is presented in Fig. 6. The CASPER QoE modelling tool is composed of the following components (see Fig. 7):

- An android application
- A google firebase synchronised with the application
- A web service to download the collected data to an editable local my SQL base
- A php/matlab tool to elaborate on the collected data and apply data analysis.

Fig. 7: The ingredients of the CASPER QoE modelling tool.

C. Network-side QoE monitoring and signalling

Moreover, CASPER has proposed a QoE-based SDN controller on top of a Mininet network topology, presented at Fig. 8. The main functionality of the controller is to guarantee a minimum QoE level for the end-users, at situations of high network congestion that lead to intense packet losses. This guarantee is achieved by triggering traffic redirection from the main (shortest) to a failover path. In order to achieve that, the controller periodically collects statistics from the network switches in order to estimate MOS as follows:

- For VoIP applications, the delay and packet loss are necessary, in order to be able to use the ITU-T G.107 E-model.
- For video applications, the bit rate, frame rate and packet loss are necessary, in order to use the ITU-T G.1070 E-model.

Fig. 8: Traffic forwarding according to QoE Monitoring [6]

Then, if MOS is lower than a predefined threshold, the controller will provoke the traffic redirection to the failover path through the insertion of appropriate rules to the OpenFlow switches. Indicative results in terms of MOS that present the above scenario are presented at Fig. 9:

Fig. 9: MOS comparison between cases with (red plot) and without (blue plot) the SDN Controller in VoIP traffic generation, when a link failure occurs (adopted from [6])

D. System Level Simulator - The OMNeT++ Framework

CASPER simulator builds upon INET/SimuLTE over the OMNeT++ Discrete Event Network Simulator. OMNeT++ is an extensible, modular, component-based C++ simulation library and framework, primarily developed for building network simulators.

All CASPER scenarios have been simulated in this environment, while here we present indicative results of Scenario B, i.e. a video streaming service that runs at the application layers of a variable number of users and the OTT server. Each user first sends a request to the server, which then starts transmitting the chunks of the video. The download can be executed simultaneously by one or more users or in different periods. The reference topology is shown in Fig. 10.

The QoE policy for video streaming aims at reacting to a decrease in the MOS value, due to the incipient network congestion, which increases the end-to-end delay and the packet loss rate. In this case, a path's change from the main path to the backup path is triggered if the value of MOS persistently falls below a given threshold. In parallel, we apply a second policy, aiming at increasing the throughput and then its corresponding MOS value. We can change the value of the packets size or the interval at which the OTT server sends the packets, i.e., we simulate the effects of adaptive streaming (namely, the packet's size or the send interval are adjusted at run-time continuously trying to cope with changing network conditions). At Fig. 11, we present simulation results for this scenario, where the vertical red lines are the markers indicating when a streaming flow has changed the path over the network, and the black vertical lines indicate the increase in the packet size.

Fig. 10: Scenario B – Network Topology [7]

Fig. 11: Average QoE metrics over time for PLR and Throughput [7]

E. CASPER testbed setup

To create the CASPER testbed environment, we have setup the following implementation components, associated with the functionality that we should provide to the testbed users:

1. An emulator platform to setup the virtual network: **Mininet**, a network emulation system, is used for this.
2. An SDN controller to control the virtual network: **POX** is used for this purpose. POX is a Python based open source OpenFlow/SDN Controller used for faster development and prototyping of new network applications [8].
3. A tool/utility to monitor/measure network performance: **Bandwidth Monitor NG** is used for this purpose. Bandwidth Monitor NG is a small live network monitor plug-in for Linux, BSD, Solaris, Mac OS X and others Operating systems [9].
4. A tool/utility to measure the application performance traversing over the network: **T-shark** network protocol analyzer is used for this purpose.
5. An analytics platform to store, visualize and push processed/aggregated data to the SDN controller for performing the network functionality over the virtual network: **ELK** (Elasticsearch, Logstash, Kibana [10]).

The CASPER testbed environment, therefore, consists of 4 virtual machines, where each one has a separate role as this is described in Table IV.

TABLE IV. VIRTUAL MACHINE ROLES

Virtual Machine	Role
ELK	Runs Elasticsearch, Kibana and Logstash
Mininet	Runs Mininet and POX controller. It also hosts all monitoring tools (tshark, fping, bw-m-ng)
Stream Server	Runs VLC
Client	Runs VLC

The virtual network topology implemented in Mininet is presented in Fig. 12. Regarding the experiments conducted in the CASPER testbed, a video file is being streamed from Stream Server virtual machine (h1) towards the Client virtual machine (h2). Stream traffic should pass through the host that runs the Mininet topology. During the streaming, measurements regarding network impairments such as latency, packet loss, jitter and video performance metrics such as bandwidth and packet interval delay are collected and presented on Kibana dashboards. Additionally, network impairments such as latency, packet loss and jitter for each

topology segment can be altered in fixed intervals in order to examine the impact they have on the video quality.

Fig. 12: Virtual Topology in Mininet GUI

As an example, when we initiate streaming from virtual hosts h1 & h2 (with VLC video streaming application), only one of the links (here referred to as segments) would be active and show video traffic in terms of bandwidth traffic. If the average latency in the primary link (link number 1) is above the threshold stated (in our case the “average rtt” threshold is 0.01ms), the path will change instantly to the failover path (link numbers 2 and 3). We can see the change in our Kibana Dashboard visualization platform as shown at Fig. 13-14.

At Fig. 13, because the Controller routes the traffic from the primary to the failover path, link/segment 1 represents only traffic due to ICMP pings. If the “average rtt” threshold drops below the threshold again, the Controller will re-route traffic back to the primary path. Every time that the threshold is reached or crossed, the Controller periodically proceeds and changes the path selection based on the metrics aggregated from the ELK monitoring module.

VI. CONSORTIUM

CASPER consortium consists of 2 academic and 3 industrial partners across 3 countries: Greece, Italy and Spain. In this way, CASPER fosters the fruitful collaboration of academia and industry with the objective of developing innovative QoE-aware service management solutions and bridging the fundamental gap between academic (i.e., more theoretical, and less application-specific) and industrial (i.e., more system- and application-specific and devoted to solutions that can be implemented in real devices) research. In particular, CASPER builds a bridge among experts in: i) designing advanced theoretical algorithms, ii) developing and implementing middleware architectures in testbeds, and iii) developing and implementing software applications and hardware drivers. The industrial beneficiaries (WEST Aquila, IQUADRAT and ADAPTERA) have strong technical background on the development of advanced middleware architectures for service provisioning and CEM schemes. Also, the academic beneficiaries (University of Athens and University of L’Aquila), have experience in design methodologies and algorithms for service and network management, as well as in QoE analysis. Apart from the technical impact of CASPER, the consortium also commits on disseminating the project results to the technical as well as the non-expert audience².

² <http://gain.di.uoa.gr/casper/dissemination.html>

Fig. 13: Bandwidth from video streaming – primary path

Fig. 14: Bandwidth from video streaming – failover path

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper has presented the CASPER project. We have provided an overview of the project’s mission and technical objectives, its structure and implementation logic, as well as main results in terms of QoE modelling, monitoring and management. As discussed in the paper, CASPER takes into consideration recent technological advances towards designing a practical, applicable, and integrated middleware architecture for personalised QoE provisioning by orchestrating the management of service flows. The program follows a human-centred approach, designing solutions that target at the satisfaction of the end-user when consuming a service. This approach entails a degree of personalisation in service delivery, which enforces an era of more “fair” telecommunication services. Moreover, the holistic approach of CASPER is expected to incentivize a collaboration paradigm between MNOs and OTTs, by providing a technologically feasible realization where feedback from MNOs is enabled and application-awareness is enforced. Furthermore, the final CASPER middleware architecture will be delivered as a software solution enabling its exploitation from smaller telecom players and start-ups, who by taking advantage of the results of the project will be able to create new business activities, such as specialized products for quality monitoring and benchmarking. The presented results depict that the user experience can be significantly improved by flexibly manipulating the network flows using a QoE-based NFV/SDN-based orchestrator, while the integration of this logic into a testbed and into real-devices are currently ongoing.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been funded by the EC under the auspices of the H2020-MSCA-RISE CASPER project (grant 645393).

REFERENCES

- [1] Liotou, E., Tsolkas, D., Passas, N., & Merakos, L. (2015). Quality of experience management in mobile cellular networks: key issues and design challenges. *IEEE Communications Magazine*, 53(7), 145–153.
- [2] Tsolkas, D., Liotou, E., Passas, N., & Merakos, L. (2014). The Need for QoE-driven Interference Management in Femtocell-Overlaid Cellular Networks. In *10th International Conference on Mobile and Ubiquitous Systems: Computing, Networking and Services (MobiQuitous 2013)* (pp. 588–601).
- [3] Colarieti, A., Marotta, A., Mpervarakis, M., Pomante, L., & Tsolkas, V. (2017). QoE provisioning over mobile networks: The CASPER perspective. In *2017 IEEE 22nd International Workshop on Computer Aided Modeling and Design of Communication Links and Networks (CAMAD)* (pp. 1–5).
- [4] ETSI GS NFV-MAN 001 V1.1.1 - Network Functions Virtualisation (NFV); Management and Orchestration.
- [5] Liotou, E., Marotta, A., Pomante, L., & Ramantas, K. (2017). A middleware architecture for QoE provisioning in Mobile Networks. In *2017 IEEE 22nd International Workshop on Computer Aided Modeling and Design of Communication Links and Networks (CAMAD)* (pp. 1–5).
- [6] Xezonaki, M.-E., Liotou, E., Passas, N., & Merakos, L. (2018). An SDN QoE Monitoring Framework for VoIP and Video Applications. In *2018 IEEE 19th International Symposium on “A World of Wireless, Mobile and Multimedia Networks” (WoWMoM)* (pp. 1–6).
- [7] Ciabrone, D., Tennina, S., Boschi, M., Tsolkas, D., & Pomante, L. (2018). Assessing QoE-driven management policies for VoIP and Video Streaming service provisioning. In *2018 IEEE 23rd International Workshop on Computer Aided Modeling and Design of Communication Links and Networks (CAMAD)* (pp. 1–6).
- [8] <https://noxrepo.github.io/pox-doc/html/>
- [9] <https://github.com/vgropp/bwm-ng>
- [10] <https://elasticsearch-py.readthedocs.io/en/master/index.htm>